

STUDIES IN CARBOHYDRATES PART V. INVESTIGATION OF THE GUM FROM *ACACIA CATECHU**

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The gum from *acacia catechu* is composed of D-galactose (9 mols.), L-arabinose (4 mols.), D-rhamnose (3 mols.) and L-glucuronic acid (3 mols.). On hydrolysis with 10% sulphuric acid the gum yields an aldobiuronic acid, which is found to be 6-β-D-glucuronosido-D-galactose by using the methylation technique.

Acacia catechu (N. O. Leguminosae) is widely distributed throughout India. The gum obtained from the tree is regarded as a good substitute for gum arabic. However, it has not been chemically investigated so far.

The gum, as supplied by the Forest Officer, Bombay State, was in the form of nodules and was easily soluble in water, non-reducing and neutral to litmus. It could be precipitated by alcohol from its aqueous solution in the form of a white powder. It did not contain nitrogen, acetyl or methoxyl group. It gave ash (3.1%) which was mainly composed of Fe³⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ and SO₄²⁻. The gum acid was obtained almost ash-free by treating the aqueous solution of the crude gum with acidified alcohol.

The acid was non-reducing and had equiv. 1025 (ca.), $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -32° (c, 2% in 0.5% NaOH). On hydrolysis with 10% sulphuric acid it afforded L-arabinose, D-galactose, L-rhamnose and an aldobiuronic acid. These sugars were isolated in crystalline forms and their physical properties were studied. Their identity has further been confirmed by preparing their crystalline derivatives. The uronic acid is shown to be D-glucuronic acid by isolating the characteristic crystals of potassium acid saccharate by simultaneous hydrolysis and oxidation of the aldobiuronic acid according to the method of Heidelberger and Goebel (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1927, 74, 613).

To elucidate the structure of the aldobiuronic acid, it was fully methylated, initially with sodium hydroxide and dimethyl sulphate, and finally by Purdie's reagent. The fully methylated ester shows η_{inh}^{25} 1.4717; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -23° (c, 0.8% in chloroform). On hydrolysis it yielded 2:3:4-tri-O-methyl-D-galactose and 2:7:4-tri-O-methyl-D-glucuronic acid. These results indicate that the aldobiuronic acid obtained from the gum is 6-β-D-glucuronosyl-D-galactose.

The aldobiuronic acid is thus identical with the one obtained from gum arabic (Challinor, Haworth and Hirst, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 258).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The crude gum gave a viscous solution in water. It was filtered through muslin and was added to alcohol, when the gum was precipitated as a white powder. It formed a neutral solution in water which was non-reducing. The ash content was 3.1%, which gave positive tests for Fe^{3+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} . It did not contain nitrogen, methoxyl or acetyl group.

Purification of the Gum.—The gum (150 g.) was dissolved in a litre of 1% NaOH solution, filtered through cloth, made just acidic to Congo red, and was poured into alcohol (95%, 3 litres), when the gum was precipitated as a white powder. Three similar treatments afforded the gum acid with negligible ash content. It was non-reducing and possessed equiv. of 1025 (ca.). It showed positive tests for pentosans, methylpentosans and galactan. The quantitative analysis of the gum by usual methods (cf. Ingle and Bhide, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 939) gave galactose (49.9%), arabinose (17.5%), rhamnose (14.0%) and uronic anhydride (17.6%); the figures in each case being calculated for anhydro-sugar units. These results indicate that the polyuronide should be composed of nine units of galactose, four of arabinose, three of rhamnose and three of glucuronic acid. Such a polyuronide should possess an equivalent of 990 and should be composed of galactose (49.08%), arabinose (17.75%), rhamnose (14.75%) and uronic anhydride (17.76%).

Hydrolysis of the Gum by 10% H_2SO_4 .—The purified gum (4.8 g.), dissolved in 10% H_2SO_4 , was heated on a water-bath at 90°. The hydrolysis was followed by finding out the reducing power of the hydrolysate at different intervals.

Time interval	0.5 hr.	1.5 hr.	4 hrs.	7 hrs.	8 hrs.
% Reducing sugars (in terms of glucose).	29.1	58.2	77	93.7	93.7

On working out the hydrolysate according to the procedure described by Ingle and Bhide (*loc. cit.*), the non-acidic reducing sugars (A) and the barium salt of the uronic acid (B) obtained were examined as follows.

Examination of the Non-acidic Reducing Sugars (A).—Chromatographic examination of the sugar syrup (A) indicated the presence of galactose, arabinose and rhamnose. The identity of these sugars was confirmed by running authentic specimens side by side. The sugar mixture was dissolved in ethyl alcohol (90%), and different crops were separated. The first two crops on further crystallisation gave D-galactose, m. p. and mixed m. p. 163°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +82° (c, 2% in water). Its α -methylphenylhydrazone melted at 186°. The remaining crops mainly contained L-arabinose, which was purified by crystallisation, m. p. and mixed m. p. 158°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +108° (c, 2% in water); its diphenylhydrazone melted at 201°. The mother-liquor on keeping for several weeks gave crystals of L-rhamnose monohydrate, m. p. 96-97°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -8° (c, 0.8% in water). It formed the characteristic *p*-bromophenylhydrazone, m. p. 217°.

Examination of the Barium Salt (B).—The barium salt, free from non-acidic reducing sugars, had $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -2° (c, 2% in water); Ba, 16.2%. The barium salt of aldobiuronic acid *i.e.*, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_3\text{Ba}$, requires Ba, 16.1%. On further hydrolysis by 10% H_2SO_4 , the aldobiuronic acid gave a non acid reducing sugar which was

identified as galactose chromatographically, but the barium salt obtained was found to contain 16 to 17% Ba, indicating that it was mainly an aldobiuronic acid and the monouronic acid formed had decomposed. Hence, the uronic acid component was identified by the following method (cf. Heidelberger and Goebel, *loc. cit.*).

The barium salt (B) (2 g.) was dissolved in water (20 c.c.) and barium ions were removed by adding a slightly less than the required quantity of $N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. The solution after filtration was diluted by $2N\text{-HBr}$ (50 c.c.) and bromine (0.5 c.c.) was added to it. The solution was refluxed for about 40 hours. It was necessary to replace bromine from time to time. At the end, the liquid did not reduce Fehling's solution. It was concentrated under reduced pressure, treated with Ag_2CO_3 , filtered and heated with H_2S , and the filtrate, thus obtained, was concentrated to a small bulk. On keeping for two days, no crystals of mucic acid were obtained, while the crystals of potassium acid saccharate separated when the concentrate was treated with 60% KOH and acetic acid.

Methylation of the Barium Salt of Uronic Acid (B).—The barium salt (B) (25 g.) was methylated by NaOH and dimethyl sulphate four times and the chloroform-soluble methylated acid was fully methylated and esterified by silver oxide and methyl iodide, yield 15 g., OMe, 50.2%. The product, when distilled under reduced pressure, furnished the following fractions. Fraction I, b.p. $140\text{-}150^\circ/5$ mm., yield 3 g. Fraction II, b.p. $255^\circ\text{-}260^\circ/5$ mm., yield 8.5 g. Residue, 3.1 g. (which was not further worked out).

Fraction I was a yellowish liquid having OMe, 59.1%, η_{sp}^{25} , 1.4489. It was shown to be methyl ester of 2:3:4-tri-*O*-methyl methyl-D-glucuronoside by preparing its amide, which crystallised from ethanol-ether, petroleum ether mixture, m. p. 186° ; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, $+136^\circ$ (*c*, 0.8% in water); N, 5.57%, OMe, 48.5%. The amide of 2:3:4-tri-*O*-methyl- α -methyl-D-glucuronoside melts at 183° ; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, $+137.5^\circ$ (*c*, 0.7% in water) (Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1732), N, 5.6%, OMe, 49.8%. The mixed m. p. of this amide and the authentic sample prepared from D-glucuronic acid remained unchanged.

Fraction II was obtained as a viscous syrup having OMe, 52.9%; equiv. 460; η_{sp}^{25} , 1.4717; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -23° (*c*, 0.8% in chloroform); $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, $-3^\circ.1$ (*c*, 0.9% in water), indicating that it might be the fully methylated methyl ester of 6- β -D-glucuronoside-D-galactose, which requires OMe, 53%; equiv., 468; η_{sp}^{25} , 1.4715; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -24° (*c*, 2% in chloroform). (Challinor *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). On hydrolysis, the ester yielded (i) 2:3:4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose, identified chromatographically by running the authentic sample side by side, and by preparing its anilide, m.p. and mixed m. p. 165° and (ii) 2:3:4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucuronic acid, identified by preparing methyl ester of 2:3:4-tri-*O*-methylsaccharolactone, m. p. and mixed m. p. $108\text{-}109^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, $+90^\circ$ (*c*, 1% in water). (cf. Parikh, Ingle and Bhide, *this Journal*, 1956, 33, 127).